

Atomic force microscopy : applications to nanobiotechnology^ψ

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Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) is a microscopic technique belonging to the Scanning Probe Microscopy (SPM) family. Other SPM techniques are Near-Field Scanning Optical Microscopy (NSOM), Electrostatic Force Microscopy (EFM) and Magnetic Force Microscopy (MFM). AFM is a useful and powerful tool for studying the morphological, dynamic, and mechanical properties of biological samples, such as, living cells, biomacromolecules, and tissues under different conditions, e.g., air, liquid, and vacuum. In this article an overview of the AFM technique is first presented and then some of its applications to nanobiotechnology are discussed. Attention is focused on the morphological and physiological studies of microbial cells and biomolecules. Some of the most important results on intermolecular interactions obtained in the past ten years, and force spectroscopy measurements of the viscoelastic properties (microrheology) of soft samples, such as, living cells, are also discussed.

Understanding the structure, function, and physical and mechanical properties of biological systems has always been the desire of biologists and biophysicists. Nowadays, many different techniques are available which can help scientists to gain new insights in to the structure and function of (e.g., X-ray diffraction¹, small angle neutron scattering², and electron microscopy³), as well as to elucidate the forces governing specific molecular interactions between (e.g., surface force apparatus⁴, pipette suction⁵, magnetic beads⁶, and optical tweezers⁷) biomolecules, cells, and protein membranes. Nevertheless, these techniques do not allow either investigating the physical and mechanical properties of biological samples or manipulating them.

Scanning probe microscopes (SPMs) can make up this lack. In particular, atomic force microscope (AFM), one of the most used SPM techniques in biology and biophysics, is not only capable to image cells⁸⁻¹⁴ and individual biomolecules¹⁵⁻²⁰, but also to manipulate them²¹⁻²⁴.

The huge success of AFM in nanobiotechnology stems from the fact that (i) its capability to work in liquids allows the biological structures to be studied in their native environments²⁵, (ii) its excellent signal-to-noise ratio provides images of very high (<1 nm) resolution^{13,14,16,26-28} that can even permit direct observation

of conformational changes of single biomolecules²⁹⁻³¹, (iii) due to its nN to pN sensitivity in measuring the forces, unbinding events of individual ligand-receptor bonds and unfolding events of single molecules can be precisely detected³²⁻³⁷, (iv) its flexibility to combine force-spectroscopy with both static and dynamic modes expands its applications to study a variety of properties, such as cell-cell and cell-substrate adhesion³⁸⁻⁴², mechanical and microrheological properties of biological samples, such as their elasticity (property of a material which causes it to be restored to its original shape after applying a mechanical stress), viscosity (resistance of a fluid to deformation under shear stress), and viscoelasticity⁴³⁻⁴⁷ (when materials change with time they respond stress as if they are a combination of elastic solids and viscous fluids), and (v) its capability to combine with other techniques, such as inverted (AFM-IM), fluorescence (AFM-FM)²³, and total internal reflection fluorescence (AFM-TIRFM) microscopes⁴⁸, gives it additional precision in localisation of biological samples. Applications of AFM in nanomedicine and nanosurgery are also fast catching up.

This review gives the latest developments in the field of AFM and its applications to nanobiotechnology. In Section 2, an overview of the AFM technique is given, while Section 3 is devoted to a critical review of the

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

applications of different modes of AFM, such as imaging, force spectroscopy, and nanomanipulation. Section 4 summarises the results and discusses future novel applications of AFM and its innovative developments.

1. Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

AFM⁴⁹ is a microscopic technique that belongs to the Scanning Probe Microscopy (SPM) family. SPM spawns from the Scanning Tunnelling Microscopy (STM) invented in 1981 by Binnig, Rohrer, Gerber, and Weibel⁵⁰ (Fig. 1) that resulted in the development of a number of microscopic techniques, such as NSOM⁵¹, EFM, MFM⁵², and AFM⁴⁹.

Fig. 1. Pictorial scheme of different main types of Scanning Probe Microscopes (SPMs).

The invention of SPM has completely changed the way we study the structure and properties of surfaces, thereby, revolutionising several fields, such as material sciences, semiconductor physics, biology, electrochemistry, biochemistry, organic chemistry, tribology, micro-mechanics, and nanotechnology.

One of the main features of SPM is that it provides three-dimensional (3-D), real-space images of surfaces at high spatial (nanometer scale) resolution in air, gas, liquid, vacuum, and under cryogenic temperatures (cryo-AFM)^{53,54}. In particular, the cryo-AFM operates in liquid nitrogen vapour that allows higher resolutions than are possible with the AFM at room temperature. This is due to the reduced thermal fluctuations and increased rigidity of the sample at lower temperatures.

Usually, the resolution that can be achieved by using an SPM goes down to the atomic level (i.e., even the atoms can be imaged), the only limitations being the flatness and cleanliness of the sample. Moreover, SPMs allow one to perform force spectroscopy experiments that can probe the interactions within a single and between different biomacromolecules.

SPM generates images of a surface, and is based on the detection of the local interaction between a small tip

probe and a small area of the surface.

Although, Electron Microscopy (EM) allows visualizing the details of biological samples at atomic resolution, the main drawback of this technique is the requirement to work in relatively high vacuum conditions. In comparison to the EM, one of the most important advantages of SPMs is their capability to image biological samples at high resolution without destroying the samples. Another disadvantage of EM overcome by SPMs, concerns the intrinsic contrast of biological materials. Indeed, this contrast is so low that contrast-enhancing agents (i.e., negative stains) are often required. SPMs, therefore, provide complimentary techniques to the traditional methods usually employed to investigate atomic structures and local properties of a variety of samples.

Nowadays, SPMs are one of the most used microscopic techniques appearing in a lot of publications covering a wide range of disciplines, in particular biology where the AFM dominates. The success of the AFM in studying biological samples lies in its nonintrusive characteristic and capability to image specimens in air or liquid. These operating features allow the real-time analysis of biological specimens/phenomena in physiological conditions⁵⁵.

STM is powerful for investigating the structure of semiconductor surfaces in ultrahigh vacuum. However, its success in biology is limited due to the fact that the insulating samples have to be coated with a metal film prior to analysis, and this causes problems while working in liquids.

NSOM imaging gives resolutions similar to EM, and works by linking the principles of operation of conventional optical microscopy with SPM techniques, in particular, AFM. NSOM also had a limited success in biology.

Because of the limitations on the use of EFM, MFM, and NSOM in studying biological systems/phenomena these techniques will not be discussed further in this article.

1.1. The principle, design and construction of SPM :

The principle of operation of any SPM is based upon scanning a fine tipped probe just above a sample surface and monitoring some interaction between the probe and the surface (Fig. 2). Generally, any SPM consists of five components : tip, scanner, detector, electronic control system, and vibration isolation system.

The nature of the probe and the property being measured determine the type of SPM to be used. For ex-

Fig. 2. Principle of operation of any SPM. A fine-tipped probe raster scans the sample surface. x -, y -, and z -movements of the tip are caused by the piezo actuator.

ample, in the STM the property is the tunnelling current, while in the NSOM it is the interaction between the light, going through an orifice that is much smaller than the wavelength of the light, and the surface. Finally, in the AFM the property is the deflection of a cantilever resulting from the tip-sample interaction. The property relevant to the SPM used is measured and then either used directly to form an image of the surface, or used as input signal for a feedback control mechanism (integrated in the electronic control system) to maintain constant either the separation distance or the force between the tip and the sample.

The scanner, also called piezoelectric actuator, is one of the most important parts of a SPM. It is made from piezoelectric materials, which alter their dimensions when high voltages are applied.

The modern SPMs are based on tube scanner geometry. The commonly used material for a piezoelectric actuator is PZT (lead zirconium titanate). The two main features, which characterize a scanner are the scan range and resonance frequency. The scan range depends upon the piezoelectric material, the scanner dimensions, and the applied voltage range. Generally, if one wants to increase the scan range the best thing to do is to increase the piezoelectric constant rather than the scanner size. The resonance frequency is determined by the stiffness of the piezoelectric actuator and the mass distribution within it. It is the most important parameter in the design of any SPM because it limits the scan rate and determines the stability with respect to mechanical vibrations. The higher resonance frequency, typical of tube scanners (12–20 kHz), is most advantageous because it allows faster scanning.

The drawback of the tube scanners is their inherent nonlinearity. Indeed, because of the hysteresis the relation between the applied voltage and the piezoelectric actuator's motion is not unique. Generally, when the SPMs are used for precise metrological measurements, such as

force spectroscopy, high position repeatability is required. This can be achieved by combining a piezoelectric actuator with a measurement system or a movement sensor. There are different types of movement sensors, such as strain gauge, inductive and capacitive sensor. Because of their high dynamics, the piezoelectric actuators along with a measurement system are well suited to a closed loop system. The closed-loop scanners measure scanner displacements and feed these data back to the electronic controller. The only drawback of the closed-loop actuators concerns the reduction in the maximum scan speed due to the limitations in the feedback bandwidth.

The piezoelectric actuator can be used to move either the tip or the sample. Generally, when large samples are used it is better to move the tip in order to reduce the inertial loading on the scanner. The sensitivity of the sample-tip approach mechanism is crucial to the best operation of SPMs.

To obtain optimum results, a vibration isolation setup is required. Usually, the desired resolution in SPM imaging is 0.01 nm in z and 0.1 nm in x , y . This means that noise from any source must be less than 0.001 nm in z and 0.01 nm in x , y .

Mechanical vibrations are a large component of the noise and those that reach the sample-tip system originate from the building⁵². Typical building vibrations are in the range 5–100 Hz. Frames, walls, and floors of buildings undergo shear and bending vibrations. Usually, higher floors exhibit larger vibrational amplitudes than the ground floor. Moreover, attention must be paid to the floor response to people walking, doors closing, nearby elevator operation, and traffic on the roads outside. The room where the SPM is housed, and the table on which it sits can have additional vibrations in the range 30–100 Hz, which can be caused, for example, by acoustic waves.

1.2. The principle of AFM :

AFM⁴⁹ is the most used SPM technique in biology these days. This is clearly reflected by the ever-increasing number of publications^{56,57} since 1996. The main advantage of AFM over STM lies in its ability to image both conducting and non-conducting samples.

The principle of operation of AFM is very simple. AFM detects deflections of a cantilever, with a sharp tip near its end that is in physical contact with the sample surface, which is being raster scanned by the tip (Fig. 3).

The cantilever obeys the Hooke's law, $F = k \cdot x$, where F is the force on the cantilever, k its spring constant, and x its deflection. This relationship allows one to obtain the

resultant force between the tip and the sample surface, provided that the spring constant of the cantilever is known and its deflection measured.

Many different techniques to measure the cantilever deflection exist, the most commonly used being the optical beam deflection^{58,59}. The main parts of an AFM using this technique are : cantilever, laser diode, and photodiode.

A laser diode of a few mW power generates a laser beam, which is reflected off the back side of a reflective (gold- or aluminium-coated) cantilever. A four- or two-segments photodiode measures the location of the reflected beam. Usually the photodiode is a PSD (Position Sensitive Detector), which can measure both normal bending and torsion of the cantilever, corresponding to normal and lateral forces.

Fig. 3. Principle of operation of an AFM. The deflection of a cantilever with a pyramidal sharp tip is measured while raster scanning across the sample surface. To measure this deflection a laser beam is reflected off the back side of the cantilever and detected by a four-segment photodiode. The cantilever obeys the Hooke's law, $F = kx$, where F is the force on the cantilever, k its spring constant, and x its deflection.

Generally, a 4-segments PSD is used for imaging because the 3-D topography of the sample surface is given by the curve $z = f(x, y)$ where x , and y are the two directions in which the tip is raster scanning the sample surface, and z is the vertical movement of the tip, which is driven by a computer-controlled piezoelectric translator.

A 2-segments photodiode is normally employed when the AFM is used in force spectroscopy mode. In this case, the cantilever is moved in the z direction, i.e., first moved downwards until a contact between the tip and the sample surface is established, and then upwards until no interactions between the tip and the surface are detected. The plot of the cantilever deflection as a function of the separation between the tip and the specimen is called force-distance curve. Using the AFM in force spectroscopy

mode allows one to measure the attractive and repulsive forces between the tip and the sample surface in order to study the chemical, physical, and mechanical properties of the specimen, such as the adhesion, the elasticity, and the dynamic strengths of molecular adhesion bonds.

1.2.1. Cantilevers and tips :

The cantilever is the key element of the AFM technique. Choosing the most suitable cantilever for the sample that one wants to study is crucial.

When the AFM is used in imaging mode, it is necessary to keep in mind that the resolution of an image is determined by the sharpness of the tip apex and the deformation of the sample under the tip pressure⁶⁰. The fabrication of a very good AFM cantilever and tip is, therefore, very important.

Generally, a tip is fabricated along with a silicon (Si), silicon dioxide (SiO_2) or silicon nitride (Si_3N_4) cantilever by using the microfabrication⁶¹ and lithography techniques^{62,63}. Since the tip is fabricated at the same time as the cantilever, both are usually made of the same material. The silicon nitride is the most used material to fabricate cantilever that is commonly employed to scan very soft specimens, such as biological samples (living cells, DNA, etc.).

The shape of an AFM cantilever (Fig. 4) can be triangular (V-shaped cantilever) or rectangular (beam cantilever) and its dimensions can range from 100–500 μm in length, 10–50 μm in width, and 0.5–5 μm in thickness. According to the dimensions of the cantilever, its spring constant, k , varies. The longer and thinner the cantilever, the smaller is the spring constant. Generally, when the specimen under study is very soft (e.g., living cells), it is necessary to use a cantilever with a very low spring

Fig. 4. (a) AFM beam cantilever. L is the length, w , the width, and t , the thickness of the cantilever. F represents the position of the force charging the cantilever; (b) V-shaped AFM cantilever. L is the length, and w , the width of the cantilever. d is the width of the rectangular beam. F represents the position of the force charging the cantilever.

constant ($k \leq 0.1$ N/m) in order to minimise the possibility to damage (e.g., scratching, or inelastically deforming) the sample surface during scanning. On the contrary, if the sample is hard (e.g., a mineral) a cantilever with a very high spring constant (100 N/m $\leq k \leq 460$ N/m) is needed.

Recently, small cantilevers with lengths of 9–50 μm , widths of 3–5 μm , and thicknesses of 86–102 μm have been developed^{64,65}. It has been shown that by using small cantilevers one can observe and measure the individual protein interactions in a faster (with more speed) and quieter (noise free) way^{64,65}. That is crucial when the rate is very important, such as in folding-unfolding experiments^{66,67}. Viani *et al.*⁶⁸ have shown that small cantilevers can be a powerful tool for studying protein dynamics at the single molecule level.

Another parameter characterising an AFM cantilever to be used is its resonance frequency ω_0 (10 kHz $\leq \omega_0 \leq 600$ kHz). The quality factor, Q , is a very important parameter to consider when choosing an AFM cantilever. In particular, the greater the Q -factor, the higher the AFM sensibility. The quality factor, $Q = \omega_0/\Delta\omega$, where $\omega_0 = \sqrt{k/m}$ is the resonance frequency of the AFM cantilever, $\Delta\omega$ is the width of the resonant peak, and m is the mass of the tip.

The Q -factor of the cantilever resonance can be increased or decreased by changing the effective properties of the force sensor (cantilever) by an electronic device, called the Q -control. The Q -control is an active resonance controller that allows one to fine-tune the response of the cantilever to any interaction, thereby, improving the sensitivity of a SPM by a factor of ~ 1000 , producing superior images in liquids, and scanning faster.

In order to obtain a high-resolution AFM image, the lateral (or frictional) forces experienced by the cantilever have to be very small. V-shaped cantilevers are more used than beam cantilevers for imaging in contact mode, because their mechanical stability with respect to torsional forces is greater. Nevertheless, detecting these lateral forces becomes crucial in the lateral friction microscopy (LFM), where the frictional force is analysed at the nanoscale by measuring the friction coefficient and the shear stress⁶⁹. That is why beam cantilevers are commonly used in LFM.

Selecting the most suitable AFM cantilever is not enough, the choice of the tip is also crucial. The main parameters characterising a tip are its shape and geometry. The most common tip shapes are pyramidal, conical,

and tetrahedral. Generally, the Si_3N_4 tips are pyramidal, whereas Si and SiO_2 tips can be fabricated in the three shapes, the conical one being the most common. The main geometrical parameters to be considered when selecting a tip are its radius of curvature r , the sidewall angles θ , and its length L_{tip} (Fig. 5). Usually, a tip does not terminate at a sharp point, its end being approximated as a hemisphere, which can be described by a radius of curvature, r . This value can be taken as a rough estimate of the tip's sharpness. The tip's sidewall angles θ and length L_{tip} play a very important role in accurately imaging steep slopes and measuring the depths of pits on the sample surface. In addition, the tip must be sufficiently narrow to completely penetrate the pit and reach its bottom.

The pyramidal Si_3N_4 tips that are commonly employed for imaging in contact mode (see Section 1.3.1) have a large sidewall angle of 35° . Hence, these tips are not suitable to image rough surfaces, which have deep (> 1 μm) and narrow (< 100 nm) valleys. Nevertheless, the pyramidal Si_3N_4 tips are excellent to scan flat surfaces at a very high resolution.

Fig. 5. Sketch of an AFM tip. The tip's radius of curvature, r , sidewall angles, θ , and length, L_{tip} are shown.

In addition to cantilevers, another family of AFM probes is that of carbon nanotubes^{70,71}, which are very sharp tips fabricated by attaching multi-walled carbon nanotubes (5–20 nm in diameter and 1 μm in length) to the end of a standard silicon cantilever by means of an acrylic adhesive. There are several advantages of nanotubes over conventional AFM tips. Firstly, nanotubes have very high aspect ratio that allows one to scan very deep crevices in the sample surface. Secondly, they have a small effective radius that increases the lateral resolution of topographical imaging. In addition, nanotubes are very flexible in order to overcome the common problem of tip breakage.

1.2.2. Calibration of AFM cantilevers :

Calibrating the AFM cantilever is the first stage of

any measurement using an AFM. The aim is to know the exact value of the spring constant of the cantilever as it obeys the Hooke's law, $F = k.x$ (see Section 1.4). Many calibration methods, such as theoretical methods^{72,73}, static methods⁷⁴, and dynamic methods⁷⁵⁻⁷⁷, are available. For brevity sake, these are not discussed here, and the reader interested in the details should refer to the original literature. There is no single best calibration technique to use. Generally, the simpler the method, the more commonly it is employed.

1.2.3. Fixation techniques for AFM sample preparation :

While preparing an AFM sample it is of utmost importance that solutions of the highest purity are used in order to avoid any contamination that otherwise will adversely affect both the imaging and force spectroscopy measurements.

Additional points that must be kept in mind to work in an imaging mode are : (i) the specimen should be flat on the same distance scale as that being scanned; (ii) the maximum topographical variation must not exceed the z-range allowed by the piezoelectric translator of the AFM; (iii) the changes in the surface topography of the sample should be gradual; (iv) the specimens should be evenly distributed over the substrate, e.g., a glass slide or a mica sheet; (v) the samples must be tightly immobilised to the substrate since otherwise the tip may shift or even detach them while scanning, thereby, precluding stable imaging. This is crucial when using the AFM in contact mode.

For force spectroscopy measurements the main precaution to be taken is to immobilise very tightly the sample to the substrate in order to avoid its detachment before the end of the force registration. It is crucial, particularly when the unfolding of proteins or the adhesion force of biopolymers to a supporting surface is under investigation.

Although, a firm attachment of the sample to the substrate is required, the specimen should still have some freedom to change its conformation. This can occur during biological activity or during interaction with another sample, such as a molecule (intermolecular interactions), a protein (protein-protein interactions), or a cell (cell-cell adhesion)⁷⁸. Moreover, the anchoring of the specimen should not be too tight along considerable portion of its surface in order to avoid some undesirable denaturing effects⁷⁹⁻⁸⁴.

1.3. Different modes of operation of AFM :

The AFM can operate in three different modes : con-

tact mode, non-contact mode, and tapping modeTM (Digital Instrument trademark) or intermittent contact mode.

1.3.1. Contact mode :

Contact mode is commonly used for imaging soft samples, such as biological organisms. The tip being in direct contact with the sample surface, the cantilever undergoes both repulsive (steric) and attractive (van der Waals) forces arising from the tip-sample interactions. During scanning the cantilever undergoes a deflection. The feedback loop circuitry keeps constant the cantilever deflection to a prefixed value, which can be varied in order to change the tip-sample interaction force. When the AFM measurements are made in air, the main attractive force is due to the capillary interaction between the tip and the sample. It is, thus, not possible to choose a contact force lower than a certain threshold. To avoid this problem it is necessary to work in a liquid in which the capillary forces get eliminated.

Contact mode is most suitable to scan flat samples where lateral forces are negligible^{28-30,85,86}. Examples of flat samples usually imaged in contact mode are two-dimensional protein arrays, including membrane protein arrays^{16,87-89}.

1.3.2. Non-contact mode :

In the non-contact mode, the tip is not in contact with the sample surface. The distance between the tip and the sample is controlled by measuring the attractive (van der Waals) force. Since the attractive force is weak, the tip-sample separation is measured by means of a resonant method⁹⁰, where the AFM cantilever oscillates at a frequency ω near its own resonance frequency ω_0 . The resonance frequency is then modified by using the following formula⁹¹ :

$$\frac{d\omega}{\omega} = \frac{f'}{2k}, \quad (1)$$

where f' is the force between the tip and the surface, and k , the spring constant of the cantilever. Measuring the deviation of the resonance frequency of the AFM cantilever from its initial value allows imaging the sample.

Generally, when working in non-contact mode it is better to use hard cantilevers ($k = 0.5-100$ N/m) for both hard and soft specimens. In addition, the pyramidal tips must be as long as possible because of the long-range (van der Waals) interaction forces between the tip and the sample.

Although the resolution of the measurements in non-contact mode is less than that obtained in contact mode,

the non-contact mode allows one to minimise the artefacts due to the forces applied by the cantilever on the sample surface. In particular, the sensibility of the force measurements performed in non-contact mode depends on both the quality factor Q of the resonance and the main noise source. The smaller force variation that can be detected is given by⁹⁰

$$\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}\right)_{\min} = \frac{\sqrt{4kBk_B T}}{A \omega_0 Q}, \quad (2)$$

where A is the mean square amplitude of vibration of the AFM cantilever, B , the detection circuit bandwidth, k_B , the Boltzmann's constant, and T , the absolute temperature. Eq. (2) shows that the Q -factor must be very large (~ 100 in air, and > 10000 in the vacuum).

The main applications of the non-contact mode are the study of the electrostatic and magnetic effects, but it can also be used to analyse a variety of samples, such as biological macromolecules⁹².

1.3.3. Tapping mode :

In the tapping mode⁹³⁻⁹⁵ also, the AFM cantilever oscillates with a frequency near its resonance frequency. The difference between the two modes is in the oscillating amplitude. It is > 10 nm in the non-contact mode where the tip is oscillated just above the sample surface, and ~ 100 nm in the tapping mode where the tip is oscillated at a greater amplitude than the non-contact mode, thereby, touching the surface on each down sweep. Thus, at each oscillation cycle the tip is "captured" intermittently in the external layer of the specimen, and a repulsive contact between the tip and the sample is generated. In order that the tip does not adhere too much to the specimen during tapping, either stiff cantilevers ($k \sim 40-50$ N/m) or large oscillation amplitudes are used.

Clearly, during a part of the oscillation cycle the tip-sample interaction becomes repulsive rendering the force applied by the tip on the specimen to be in the range 0.1–1 nN, which is less than the force obtained in contact mode in air ($\sim 1-30$ nN)^{96,97}. This means that when the sample is very soft (e.g., living cells, proteins, biomacromolecules, etc.), or it is weakly anchored to the substrate, the tapping mode is more suitable than the contact mode. This is so because the tip taps gently on its surface without damaging or shifting the specimen. Another advantage of the tapping mode over the contact mode is that the lateral forces, which can decrease the resolution of the image, are nearly absent because the tip

remains in contact with the sample just for a short time.

1.4. Different application-modes of AFM :

AFM finds many applications in biology, the most important being : imaging (surface topography of the specimen); force spectroscopy (study of the folding-unfolding of proteins, and the adhesive forces of biological samples, such as proteins or living cells to a substrate, etc.); and nanomanipulation (extraction of chromosomal DNA, disruption of antibody-antigen bonds, dissection of a biological membrane, nanodissection of protein complexes, and controlled modulation of protein conformations). These are briefly described below.

1.4.1. Imaging :

Contact mode : The AFM can be operated in both *constant force* and *constant height modes*. In the constant force operation, when the tip scans the sample surface, the tip-sample force (i.e., the deflection of the cantilever) is kept constant at a pre-determined set-point value by moving either the tip or the sample (depending on the AFM setup) in the z -direction at each point. With this aim, the deflection of the cantilever is measured and used as input signal for the feedback control to maintain constant the tip-sample distance (closed-loop imaging). By recording the displacements of the tip or the sample along the z -axis one can obtain the *topographic* (or *height*) image of the sample surface. In the constant height mode, there is no feedback control (open-loop imaging), i.e., the tip and the sample cannot be moved in the z -direction. The constant height operation can be used only if the surface being scanned is flat. This is to avoid any random fluctuations in the tip-sample force that may loosen the contact between the tip and the surface or even damage the tip and/or the sample surface.

Another imaging technique that can be used in contact mode is the *error signal* or *deflection mode*. The main advantage of an error signal image over a height image is the higher resolution; the finest details being immediately identified during scanning. This high-resolution image is called error signal image because it is produced by the incapability of the feedback control to keep constant the tip-sample force (i.e., the deflection of the cantilever)⁹⁸.

The *force modulation mode*^{99,100} is another very useful imaging technique. A small z -modulation is applied to the cantilever or the sample, while the tip stays in contact with the sample surface. Similar to the contact mode, in the force modulation operation the mean imaging force is determined by the deflection of the cantilever. The difference between the two being that the deformation un-

dergone by the sample, because of the modulation signal, will depend on its viscoelastic properties¹⁰⁰. Hence, by analysing the force modulation images the mechanical properties of a specimen can be studied, but this requires information about the cantilever amplitude and the phase signal. Then, analysing these experimental data within the framework of the viscoelastic theory will permit to determine the elastic (amplitude signal) and viscous (phase signal) properties^{101,102}.

Tapping mode : A very useful imaging technique that can be employed in tapping mode is the *phase imaging*. During scanning, the relative phase angle between the driving oscillation amplitude and the cantilever deflection recorded by the photodiode is used to generate the phase image.

Similar to the constant force operation in contact mode, in tapping mode the *constant amplitude operation* is employed; the changes in oscillation amplitude as a function of the tip-sample separation being used as an input signal for the feedback control. In particular, the oscillation amplitude of the AFM cantilever is kept just below the free amplitude.

When the AFM works in the imaging mode, the set-point amplitude has to be chosen. If the set-point is just below the free oscillation amplitude, then the term "soft-tapping" is used. On the contrary, when the set-point is smaller than the free amplitude, the term employed is "hard-tapping". Usually, the set-point should not be too low in order to avoid artefacts in the image.

Imaging in aqueous fluids : The main strength of an AFM is its ability to work in both air and aqueous fluids. In biology, imaging in liquid is very important because it allows studying the biological samples in physiological environments¹⁰³. In particular, it is not only possible to analyse a specimen under conditions where its structure is native (e.g., DNA, proteins, etc.), but also in an environment where it can maintain its biological activity (e.g., living cells).

Although the contact mode is commonly employed to image biological samples in aqueous fluids because it is the simplest mode to use, the tapping mode is also used often due to its ability to reduce lateral forces. The best results are usually obtained by using softer cantilevers (~ 0.1 N/m) in contact mode than those employed for tapping mode in air (~ 40 N/m)⁹⁴.

Tapping mode in liquid can be very tricky to set up. The main problems that must be dealt with are the following. Firstly, the resonance frequency of an AFM cantilever in liquids is lower than that in air. This is because

of the added mass of the liquid. Secondly, the Q -factor is very low (near one) because the cantilever is completely damped.

A direct consequence of these troubles is the loss of mechanical gain at resonance, and the so-called "forest of peaks" effect, which limits the resolution achievable by using the tapping mode in liquid⁹⁴.

To overcome these problems, a large amplitude acoustic signal, usually generated by a transducer attached to the cantilever holder, is used to drive the cantilever. This acoustic signal excites mechanical resonances in both the cantilever holder and the liquid, and thus the response is a combination of these resonances and the intrinsic response of the cantilever⁹⁴. The disadvantage caused by this complicated signal is that it limits the smallest amplitude of oscillation that can be detected.

Another implementation of the tapping mode in liquid is the so-called magnetic AC mode (MAC modeTM)¹⁰⁴. In order to operate at very small amplitudes of vibration, the tip is driven directly rather than using excitations of the liquid to drive it. The cantilever is coated with a magnetic film and a force is directly applied to the cantilever by using a solenoid placed under the sample. The advantage of the MAC mode over the tapping mode in liquid is that in the MAC mode AFM the "forest of peaks" does not appear; the response from the photodiode being a single resonance peak¹⁰⁴. As a consequence, it is possible to use smaller amplitudes of oscillation than in tapping mode, and thus to image very soft and weakly bound samples. In addition, the resolution achieved by using the MAC mode is much higher than that obtained in tapping mode in liquid. This is due to the fact that the asperities on the very end of the AFM tip remain intact, and thus they can be used as super-sharp probes¹⁰⁴.

1.4.2. Force spectroscopy :

One of the most exciting developments of the AFMs is the force spectroscopy, in which the very high sensitivity of the AFM is used to measure the interaction forces (~ 10 pN–100 nN) between two opposite surfaces (e.g., the AFM tip and the sample surface)¹⁰⁵. The main aim of the force spectroscopy is to elucidate the chemical, physical and mechanical properties of the specimen, such as adhesion, elasticity, and binding/rupture force between the AFM probe and the sample surface.

The AFM instrumentation employed to perform force measurements is similar to that used for imaging (AFM cantilever, laser, and photodiode), the only difference being that during a force spectroscopy experiment the cantilever is moved just along the z -direction, and not in

x , y , and z as done in the imaging mode.

Usually, the force measurements are carried out in contact mode, even though it is possible to use one of the intermittent modes (non-contact or tapping). In particular, measuring the oscillation amplitude of the AFM cantilever as a function of the tip-sample distance allows one to investigate the electromagnetic fields on the sample surface, as well as its viscoelastic properties.

Force-distance curves : The main outcome of a force spectroscopy experiment is the force-distance curve, which shows the force experienced by the cantilever both when the AFM probe (AFM tip or a microsphere glued onto the cantilever) is brought in contact with the sample surface and separated from it (Fig. 6). The trend of a force-distance curve depends on the loading rate (force/time) on the AFM cantilever. The probe-sample distance is defined as the difference between the piezo displacement in the z -direction and the deflection undergone by the cantilever. If the sample is soft (e.g., a living cell) it is necessary to take into account the sample deformation also.

In the following, the different parts of a generic force-distance curve (Fig. 6) are described⁷⁸. Two cycles can

Fig. 6. Sketch of a force-distance curve. The force represents the deflection undergone by the AFM cantilever, while the distance is the tip-sample separation. f^* is the adhesion force, i.e., the rupture force between the tip and the sample surface. Sketches of the different steps of a force spectroscopy experiment are also provided. (A) At the beginning of a force measurement, the tip and the sample are far away from each other; (B) when the tip and the sample begin to come closer together, the tip jumps-to-contact, due to the attractive forces; (C) moving further towards the sample, the tip starts to undergo a deflection due to the repulsive tip-sample interaction (linear part of the force-distance curve); (D) when the tip is separated from the sample, the tip still stays in contact with the sample surface, owing to the adhesion force between the tip and the sample; (E) when the tip and the sample are detached from each other, the adhesion peak appears whose height corresponds to the tip-sample adhesion force.

be easily distinguished : approach cycle and retract cycle.

Approach cycle :

- (A) At the beginning of a spectroscopy experiment, the probe and the sample are not in contact as the probe is far away from the sample surface. Hence, no interaction between the two surfaces occurs.
- (B) When the probe is close to the sample surface, forces between atoms on the two surfaces begin to act. This causes the flexible cantilever to bend until its elastic (reversible) force equals the probe-sample interaction force and the system is in equilibrium. The probe-sample attractive force induces the probe to come in contact with the sample surface (jump-to-contact). This can occur even from a large distance before the expected time of contact, and if this attractive force is absent, the jump-to-contact can limit the data that may obtained during the approach cycle.
- (C) Once the probe and the sample are in contact, the cantilever undergoes an increasing repulsive force as the electron orbitals of the atoms in the probe and the sample surface begin to overlap. The cantilever therefore bends and its deflection increases as the probe presses against the sample surface. This zone of the force-distance curve is called contact region. At this time of the spectroscopy experiment, the cantilever and/or the sample surface may experience an elastic (reversible) and/or plastic (irreversible) deformation, which may yield some information about the mechanical (elastic and viscoelastic) properties of the sample.

Retract cycle :

- (D) When the AFM cantilever is loaded (controlled force), the cantilever being more or less bent, the process described above is reversed and the probe is withdrawn from the sample surface.
- (E) During the retract cycle different forces can be measured, such as adhesion (created when the probe is in contact with the surface) and hydrophobic (appears when hydrophobic samples are studied in water) forces. The adhesion force, one of the most investigated, is measured from the deflection of the cantilever just before the jump-off-contact point (Fig. 6). Jump-off-contact occurs when the spring constant of the cantilever overcomes the adhesive probe-sample interactions; the force-distance curve showing the so-called

adhesion peak. The height of the adhesion peak gives the adhesion force f^* . The importance of the adhesion force lies in the fact that its evaluation allows comparing the interaction strengths of different atomic arrangements within molecules or between molecules.

Analysis of the force-distance curves obtained from an AFM spectroscopy experiment can give a lot of information^{78,81,106}. Force spectroscopy experiments have been widely performed to study : (i) intermolecular interactions, such as receptor-ligand interactions^{32,40,107,108}, and antigen-antibody interactions^{33,35,36,109}; (ii) intramolecular interactions, e.g., stretching of a variety of biological polymers, including polysaccharides¹¹⁰, proteins¹¹¹⁻¹¹⁴, and DNA^{34,115}. Even the unfolding of multi-domain protein molecules or individual protein domains^{116,117} has been extensively investigated; (iii) microrheology that concerns the microscopic measurements of viscoelastic properties, and these studies have been performed recently on biological samples¹¹⁸ and (iv) interactions between cells, such as measurements of the cell-cell adhesion where the AFM probe is replaced by a living cell³⁸.

Force mapping : Another very important application of force spectroscopy is the force mapping (or force volume imaging)^{105,119}. Force mapping combines force measurements and imaging. A force mapping data set contains an array of force curves and a sample image as well. It can be used to obtain a 2D or 3D map of the interaction forces between the AFM probe (tip or a microsphere glued onto the cantilever) and the sample surface.

Some differences exist between a single force-distance curve and a force mapping image : (i) a single force curve records the interaction force between the AFM probe and the sample surface as it approaches to and retracts from a single point on the surface. A force mapping data set contains an array of force curves over the entire sample area; (ii) a single force curve is measured at a unique x - y position on the sample surface. The force curves contained in a force mapping data set are from an array of x - y positions, and these are then combined into a 3D array of force data to form a 3D map.

The main advantages of the force mapping are the capability to collect force curves at different z positions and thousands of x - y positions during a single image scan, the opportunity to correlate the sample surface topography to the interaction force between the AFM probe and the surface, and to obtain a better quantization of the interaction force. These types of force measurements yield

information about the elasticity^{101,102,120,121} and adhesion^{120,122-124} of a biological sample, as well as the electrostatic¹²⁵⁻¹²⁷, and binding¹²⁸⁻¹³⁰ properties of the specimen¹⁰⁵. Recently, it has also been suggested that the force mapping mode should be used whenever the height or volume of the soft samples needs to be accurately determined¹³¹.

1.4.3. Nanomanipulation :

Nanomanipulation is based on scanning probe microscopy (SPM) and, in particular, on scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM)¹³². Generally, nanomanipulation refers to the ability of a SPM to manipulate atoms, molecules, and nanostructures in a very precise way. In particular, when applied to life sciences, SPM nanomanipulation (nanobiomanipulation) allows nanodissection of isolated biomolecules (e.g., DNA), plasma membranes, individual protein subunits, viruses, and cells^{18,133-137}. Eigler and coworkers¹³⁸ (1990) used an STM tungsten tip to position 35 xenon atoms onto a nickel surface in order to form the word "IBM".

Two different techniques can be distinguished for manipulating atoms on a surface using an STM¹³² : (i) parallel technique in which the STM tip moves the atoms along the surface and positions them at a desired point. The motion of the atom/molecule adsorbed on to STM tip is parallel to the substrate surface, hence the name "parallel technique". The bond between the manipulated atom/molecule and the surface is never broken; (ii) perpendicular technique where the atom/molecule adsorbed on to the STM tip is first lifted from the substrate surface, and then moved above the surface to a desired point where the atom/molecule is dropped from the tip.

The AFM is also widely used in nanomanipulation, the advantage over the STM being that even non-conductive specimens, such as biomolecules or cells can be manipulated by AFM¹⁸. The atoms and molecules of a sample surface are manipulated by dragging the AFM tip across the surface itself.

2. Applications of AFM to nanobiotechnology

2.1. Nanobiomanipulation :

Nanobiomanipulation using an AFM is based on the possibility to control, at a nanometer scale, the position and the force of the cantilever. As mentioned above (see Section 1.4.3), one of the main applications of nanobiomanipulation is the dissection of biological structures.

In 1992, two different research groups succeeded in

nanomanipulating DNA both in air¹³⁹ and in propanol¹⁴⁰ by using an AFM. The isolated DNA, adsorbed on a mica surface, was nanodissected by increasing the force applied to the AFM tip to about 5 nN. Also, chromosomes can be dissected in order to extract genetic material from them^{141,142}. In particular, the chromosomes can be dissected at selected positions and they can be precisely documented^{141,143}.

Another important application of AFM nanomanipulation concerns the nanodissection of plasma membranes. Generally, the cell-cell interactions involve the adhesion of two-cell membranes to each other. The extracellular regions of specific membrane proteins (MPs) mediate this adhesion¹⁸. AFM is widely used to study the native surface structure of MPs incorporated in a lipid bilayer^{88,144}, the only problem being that their extracellular surfaces must be uncovered to allow the AFM tip to scan them. The extracellular surface of the MPs from the bottom layer can be revealed by dislodging a small fraction of the upper membrane layer by increasing the force applied on the AFM cantilever¹⁸. The AFM can also be used as nanoscalpel to remove individual protein subunits, thereby, allowing to study the structures of surfaces that otherwise would be completely hidden. This feature of the AFM has been used by Fotiadis and coworkers²² (1998) to nanodissect the pigment-containing reaction center photosystem I (PSI) from the thermophilic cyanobacterium *Synechococcus* sp., which consists of 11 protein subunits. Repetitive scanning of the PSI surface displaces three extrinsic subunits out of 11, and exposes the underlying alternative luminal and stromal surfaces, making them accessible to the AFM tip²².

The AFM nanomanipulation technique has also been employed to fabricate artificial DNA patterns^{137,145}. A mechanical nanomanipulation was used to cut the DNA 2D-network to fabricate complex artificial patterns. DNA strands were then converted in to spherical nanoparticles and nanorods by pushing the DNA molecules to fold them up in ordered structures.

Nishida and coworkers⁴⁸ (2002) used an AFM-TIRFM system to perform cellular-level manipulations using AFM, and then to detect and confirm these results by using the detection apparatus of the TIRFM. The AFM-TIRFM system was used as a precise intracellular injector to inject fluorescent beads in the nuclear region of a living cell. The system could clearly show the presence of fluorescent beads in the nucleus of the cell. This AFM-TIRFM system may have future applications in nanobiotechnology, such as the precise manipulation of single DNA mole-

cules.

AFM is extensively used to extract DNA by chromosomal dissection for cytogenetic studies, such as chromosome specific molecular analysis of genes, investigations of chromosomal evolution, and studies of genetic defects. Stark *et al.*¹⁴⁶ (2003) have combined AFM and UV-laser ablation techniques to nanodissect human metaphase chromosomes both mechanically and optically by using AFM and UV-laser, respectively. A cut width of 380 nm was obtained by using the UV-laser, while AFM nanodissection gave cuts between 70 and 280 nm. These results show that while both systems provide *in situ* nanomanipulation, the precision obtained with AFM is far better. Oberringer and coworkers¹⁴⁷ (2003) strengthened further the important role played by AFM in nanodissection and nanoextraction of DNA from chromosomes. In particular, the capability of AFM in precise localisation of the material to be extracted was highlighted. This problem is fundamental in nanodissection. Hards *et al.*²³ (2005) have used an AFM-FM system to simultaneously manipulate and observe individual dye-labeled DNA molecules.

Obataya and coworkers²⁴ (2005) developed a new system for performing surgical operations on living cells by using ultrathin needle shaped AFM tips. These needles were used to penetrate both the cellular and nuclear membranes of a living cell to reach the cell nucleus. This new technique should provide a versatile method for living cell surgery, which will allow modifying the cell's functions. In particular, if used on stem cells this method could be employed to control cell's differentiation (the process by which the cells become heart cells, kidney cells, liver cells, etc.), proliferation, and division.

2.2. *Imaging microbial cell surfaces and biomolecules* :

AFM is probably one of the most used techniques to image biological samples due to its capability to directly image the specimen even under physiological conditions¹¹. The literature available on AFM imaging is too wide to be entirely covered here. This is because of the huge variety of different biological samples that can be imaged. The attention will therefore be focused on only two kinds of specimens : microbial cells (e.g., bacteria, membranes, yeast cells) and biomolecules (e.g., DNA, proteins).

2.2.1. *Imaging of microbial cell surfaces* :

AFM has not been widely used to image microbial cell surfaces so far, but imaging applications to microbiology are growing quickly¹⁴⁸.

AFM has been employed to investigate the conforma-

tional changes of native MPs, such as the hexagonally packed intermediate (HPI) layer from *Deinococcus radiodurans*, outer membrane protein F (OmpF) porin (passive pores contained in the outer membrane of bacteria that allow the uptake of small nutrients and release of metabolites), aquaporin-Z (large family of membrane channels involved in osmoregulation), bacteriorhodopsin^{57,149,150} (trans-membrane protein that functions as a light-driven proton pump), halorhodopsin¹⁵¹, (retinal protein that functions as a light-driven anion pump), and crystalline bacterial cell surface layers¹⁵². The very high signal-to-noise ratio of the AFM permitted¹⁴⁹ to image individual MPs under physiological conditions at lateral resolution of 0.5–1 nm and vertical resolution of 0.1–0.2 nm. This feature of the AFM has allowed Scheuring and coworkers¹⁵⁰ (2002) to sample the conformational space of MPs. In particular, OmpF porin, aquaporin-Z, and bacteriorhodopsin were imaged at a lateral resolution of less than 0.7 nm and a vertical resolution of about 0.1 nm.

Persike *et al.*¹⁵¹ (2001) succeeded in directly observing the 2D crystals of native halorhodopsin in aqueous solution. The images were recorded with a resolution up to 1.4 nm and found that the crystal surface showed different structures depending upon the imaging force used. This indicated that some zones of the halorhodopsin protein were stiffer than the others that were much more compressible.

The crystalline bacterial cell surface layers (S-layers)¹⁵², a very important model system, have been used to study the structure, synthesis, genetics, assembly, and function of proteinaceous supramolecular structures. S-layers find several applications in nanobiotechnology, and these range from biotechnology, biomimetics, and nanopatterning of surfaces, to the formation of ordered arrays of metal clusters/nanoparticles required for nanoelectronics applications. For a very good review on this subject the reader is referred to Ref.¹⁵².

In the past four years, much progress has been made in developing immobilisation techniques, and image acquisition of MPs in different environmental conditions and AFM operation modes^{19,153–155}. Doktycz *et al.*¹⁵⁴ (2003) used gelatine coated mica surfaces to immobilise and image both gram positive (bacteria that stain purple with the gram staining procedure), *Staphylococcus aureus*, and gram negative (bacteria that stain pink with the gram staining procedure), *Escherichia coli*, bacteria. Gelatine coated surfaces were shown to be much better than poly-L-lysine coating normally used to immobilise cells¹⁵³.

Coating the surfaces with agarose gel¹⁵⁵ to immobilise cells was found to be better than poly-L-lysine. The reason being that poly-L-lysine might interact with the cell wall and induce some structural alterations. Doktycz and coworkers¹⁵⁴ (2003) also found that when the gram negative bacteria, *Rhodopseudomonas palustris*, was imaged in liquid, it showed a smoother surface than when imaged in air. However, imaging in air revealed much more details of the bacteria surface structures, including flagella. These findings are similar to those obtained by Bolshakova and coworkers¹⁵³ (2001) who imaged *Escherichia coli* in both air and liquid, and found that imaging in air revealed many morphological details that were missing in the cells imaged in liquid. Comparison¹⁵³ of the contact, tapping, and MAC modes of AFM operation showed that the contact and MAC modes in liquid gave the best and comparable images with the finest details of the cell surface structure revealed. By contrast, the tapping mode in liquid yielded abnormally flat images of the cells. Micic *et al.*¹⁵⁵ (2004) imaged the gram negative *Shewanella oneidensis* MR-1 cells in both air and liquid by using a tapping mode AFM-FLIM (confocal fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy) system. The AFM images of the cells scanned in air rather than in liquid showed an enhancement in the contrast and signal-to-noise ratio, and these conclusions are similar to those reached by other authors (see earlier discussion).

Yeast cells are another biological system that is widely studied in microbiology. Although their morphology and ultrastructure have been extensively investigated by using different techniques, such as transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and soft X-ray contact microscopy (SXCM)¹¹, there are only a few reports of AFM imaging of yeasts^{31,156–159}. The main reason is that the AFM work requires specimens to be tightly attached to the substrate. Yeasts, however, have thick and mechanically strong cell walls, resulting in a lack of strong adherence to the substrate. Consequently, during scanning, the AFM tip might detach the cells from the substrate. A variety of immobilisation techniques, such as air-drying, chemical fixation, and confinement in agar gels or in porous membranes^{19,156,157,160} of different porosities, have been developed. Dhadwar *et al.*¹⁶¹ (2003) have also explored the possibility to modify the surface properties of cell-supporting substrates by means of the oligopeptide EAK 16 II.

One of the most studied yeast strains is *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* as it is a model organism for studies of cell

cycle, ageing, and genetic diseases¹⁶². Adya *et al.*¹³ (2005) have investigated the morphological changes in the cell envelopes of the budding yeast, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (NCYC 1681, an ale brewing strain from the National Collection of Yeast Cultures, Norwich, UK), and the fission yeast, *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* (strain DVPB 1354, from the Dipartimento Vegetale e Biologia, University of Perugia, Italy), in response to the applied thermal and osmotic stresses. AFM imaging, together with measurements of culture viability and cell size, allowed relating the yeast cell surface topological changes at the nanoscale with cellular stress physiology. These yeasts were subjected to thermal stress by exposing them to four different temperatures (0°C, 40°C, 50°C, and 90°C), and osmotic stress by exposing them to four different sorbitol concentrations (10%, 20%, 30%, and 40% w/v), for different lengths of time up to 1 h. Unstressed yeasts incubated at 25°C, and treated with 0% sorbitol acted as controls for the thermal and osmotic stresses, respectively.

For both the strains¹³, cell viability decreased quickly with increase in both the exposure time and the temperature (for thermal stress) or the sorbitol concentration (for osmotic stress). AFM images showed that *S. cerevisiae* and *Schiz. pombe* shrank when exposed to both a cold (0°C) and heat ($\geq 40^\circ\text{C}$) shock up to 1 h (Fig. 7). Exposing both the strains to low sorbitol concentrations (10% and 20%) up to 1 h did not cause any dramatic changes in their morphology. A clear change in the morphology of the yeasts was, however, observed when they were subjected to high sorbitol concentrations (30% and 40%) up to 1 h. The yeasts shrank, and their structures nearly collapsed (Fig. 8). Comparing the results obtained for the two strains, the effect on the cell size and morphology by the physical (thermal and osmotic) stresses was found to be more pronounced for *S. cerevisiae* than *Schiz. pombe*, indicating that the latter strain may be more resistant to physical stress. Adya *et al.*¹⁴ (2005) have also studied the morphological and physiological changes of the same two strains of yeasts exposed to chemical stresses (different concentrations of ethanol and H₂O₂) up to 1 h.

2.2.2. Imaging of biomolecules :

AFM has been extensively used to image biomolecular complexes in order to understand how they assemble, and thus to gain insight in to their structures and functions.

AFM has been employed to visualise the interactions of DNA with proteins. Cary *et al.*¹⁶³ (1997) imaged the

Fig. 7. Height images of *S. cerevisiae* yeast cells exposed to 0°C, 40°C, 50°C, and 90°C for 10 min, 30 min, and 1 h. The yeasts kept at room temperature (25°C) were used as a control for the thermally stressed yeast cells.

Fig. 8. Height images of *Schiz. pombe* yeast cells exposed to 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40% sorbitol (w/v) for 10 min, 30 min, and 1 h. The yeasts exposed to 0% sorbitol (w/v) were used as a control for the osmotically stressed yeast cells.

association of DNA with the DNA-dependent protein kinase (DNA-PK) and the DNA binding component Ku. It was observed that in the presence of Ku, a large number of DNA molecules formed loops. van Noort and coworkers¹⁶⁴ (1998) also used tapping mode AFM imaging to investigate the DNA-protein interactions. The dynamic interactions between DNA and photolyase were visualised by loosely immobilising both on to mica in order that the parts of the two proteins that were not attached to the surface could move during the experiment to interact with each other. The tapping tip swept up the photolyase molecules and when a DNA strand came in its way, the photolyase stuck to the DNA forming a DNA-photolyase complex, which could be visualised. Using this technique, association, dissociation, and movement of photolyase over DNA were observed.

Gaczynska *et al.*³¹ (2004) imaged the interactions between the *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* (sp) origin recognition complex (ORC) and the spOrc4 protein with the sp autonomously replicating sequence 1 (ars1). It was observed that the interaction spORC-ars1 occurred only through spOrc4.

Poma *et al.*¹⁶⁵ (2005) visualised the interactions between the plasmid DNA and saporin-SO6, which is a plant enzyme. The plasmid DNA was completely wrapped by saporin and the distribution of saporin molecules along the DNA chain was quite random.

The structure and morphology of umbravirus genomes have been studied¹⁶⁶. The genome of *Groundnut rosette virus*, a member of the genus umbravirus, differs from those of most other viruses in that it does not encode a coat protein (CP), and thus no virus particles are formed in the infected plants. Besides an RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (encoded by ORF1 and ORF2), umbravirus genomes encode two other proteins from almost completely overlapping open reading frames (ORF). One of these (encoded by ORF4) is a cell-to-cell MP that can mediate the transport of homologous and heterologous viral RNAs through plasmodesmata without the participation of a CP. The other umbravirus-encoded protein, ORF3, is a multifunctional RNA-binding protein involved in phloem-associated long-distance RNA movement, and protection from RNase attack. This protein forms filamentous ribonucleoprotein (RNP) particles containing viral RNA, which serve to protect viral RNA, and may be the form in which it moves through the phloem. Thus the ORF3 protein appears to be an umbravirus alternative to classical viral CPs¹⁶⁶. Fibrillarin is another nucleolar pro-

tein, which is present in abundance and involved in many post-transcriptional processes, including processing and modification, and methylation of pre-ribosomal RNA (rRNAs), and ribosome assembly. As a first step towards understanding the molecular structures and functions of these proteins, the viral RNA, ORF3, and fibrillarin protein molecules were visualised²⁰ by using AFM (see Figs.

Fig. 9. AFM analysis of *umbravirus* encoded RNA molecules reveals small globular structures (Av. 50 nm diameter and 6 nm height) for these protein molecules.

Fig. 10. AFM image of ORF3 protein molecules. Smooth small globules (Av. 20 nm diameter and 9 nm height) can be visualised.

Fig. 11. AFM image of fibrillar protein molecules form globules (Av. 35 nm diameter and 11 nm height).

9-11). Further work to study the complexes formed between these proteins by AFM is underway.

2.3. Force spectroscopy :

2.3.1. Intra- and inter-molecular interactions and cell adhesion measurements :

Intra- and inter-molecular interactions :

In the past ten years, many force spectroscopy experiments have been carried out in order to elucidate the unbinding forces of both individual ligand-receptor bonds (intermolecular interactions) and single molecules (intramolecular interactions). Also, cell-cell and cell-substrate interactions have been extensively studied. The number of publications on these subjects is so large that it is impossible to cover them completely in this article. Only selected examples are, therefore, discussed in this section.

Florin *et al.*³² (1994) used an AFM in force spectroscopy mode in order to measure the unbinding forces of individual biotin-avidin systems. The receptor (avidin) was attached to the pyramidal tip of the AFM cantilever, while the ligand (biotin) was fixed on to an agarose bead. The tip was then approached to the bead until a contact was established and the biotin-avidin adhesion was directly measured by analysing the deflection of the AFM cantilever during the retract cycle, i.e., when the tip was

withdrawn from the agarose bead. The force necessary to detach the tip from the bead was found to be an integer multiple of the rupture force $f^* = 160 \pm 20$ pN, which is the force required for breaking a single ligand-receptor bond.

Hinterdorfer and coworkers¹⁰⁹ (1996) measured the unbinding force between human serum albumin (HSA) antigen and polyclonal anti-HSA antibody. The antigen was fixed on to a mica surface and the antibody was covalently attached to the pyramidal tip of the AFM cantilever by means of a PEG (Polyethylene Glycol) linker molecule. The unbinding force f^* was found to be 244 ± 22 pN.

Fritz *et al.*³³ (1998) carried out force spectroscopy experiments to gain information on the rupture forces, elasticity, and kinetics of the dynamic adhesion process of single complexes of P-selectin/P-selectin glycoprotein ligand-1 (PSGL-1). The ligand molecules (PSGL-1) were immobilised on the tip of an AFM cantilever and the receptors (P-selectin) on to a substrate. It was found that the P-selectin/PSGL-1 complexes could withstand forces up to 165 pN. The rupture force and lifetime of the complexes were not constant, but depended upon the loading rate (force/time). In particular, the P-selectin/PSGL-1 complexes continued to break over a long period of time when small forces were applied. By contrast, at higher loading rates the complexes broke within a very short time.

Strunz *et al.*³⁴ (1999) measured the forces needed to mechanically separate a single DNA duplex by covalently immobilising the complementary single DNA strands on an AFM tip and a glass surface via the PEG linker molecules. Loading rates in the range of 16–4000 pN/s were used, and it was found that depending on the loading rate and sequence length, the unbinding forces of single duplexes varied from 20 to 50 pN.

Moy and coworkers^{35,167} studied the interaction between the leukocyte function associated antigen-1 (LFA-1) and the intercellular adhesion molecule-1 (ICAM-1). 3A9 cell expressing LFA-1 was attached at the end of an AFM cantilever and allowed to interact with a substrate (a tissue culture dish) covered with ICAM-1. Two types of experiments were carried out. In the first one³⁵, the unbinding forces were measured at different loading rates, and the force spectrum (i.e., unbinding forces versus loading rate) of the LFA-1/ICAM-1 interaction showed a fast and a slow loading regime. By adding Mg^{2+} (a cofactor stabilising the LFA-1/ICAM-1 complex), an increase of the unbinding force f^* in the slow regime was observed.

In the second experiment¹⁶⁷, the promotion of LFA-1 dependent cell adhesion by means of PMA (Phorbol Myristate Acetate) was studied. The observed increase (10-fold) in adhesion of PMA-stimulated cells to immobilised ICAM-1 was related to changes in the elasticity of the cell.

Moy *et al.*³⁶ (2003) studied the interaction of $\alpha_5\beta_1$ integrin with wild type fibronectin fragment FN7-10 and two mutants, viz. FN7-10 RGD (arg-gly-asp) deleted mutant and FN7-10 synergy site deleted mutant. K562 cell expressing the $\alpha_5\beta_1$ integrin was attached to the end of an AFM cantilever and fragment FN7-10 or the mutants were adsorbed on to a substrate (a tissue culture dish). The pulling force experiments were performed at different loading rates. The unbinding force of the $\alpha_5\beta_1$ /FN7-10 (wild type) complex revealed a fast (> 10000 pN/s) and a slow (< 10000 pN/s) loading regime, characterising the inner and outer activation energy of the $\alpha_5\beta_1$ /FN7-10 complex, respectively. The FN7-10 RGD (arg-gly-asp) deleted mutant suppressed both the inner and outer activation barriers, while the FN7-10 synergy site deleted mutant suppressed only the outer activation barrier of the complex. These results suggested that when the integrin was activated, a cooperative interaction with both the RGD and synergy sites occurred.

Andreev *et al.*³⁷ (2004) investigated the interactions between 3a MP of a plant virus, *Cucumber mosaic virus* (CMV), and viral RNA at a single molecule level. The behaviours of CMV wild type 3a MP and the mutant 3a Δ C33MP, where the C-terminal 33 amino acid residues of the CMV MP were deleted, were studied. The differences in the strengths of the MP-RNA systems (minimal rupture force of ~ 45 pN for the CMV wild type 3a MP-RNA system, and of ~ 90 pN for the 3a Δ C33MP-RNA complex) were attributed to the molecular binding mechanisms. The minimal intramolecular unbinding forces of both CMV wild type 3a MP and 3a Δ C33MP were ~ 50 pN and 70 pN, respectively. These results could explain why the 3a Δ C33MP-RNA complexes are more cooperative than the CMV wild type 3a MP-RNA systems. These findings are of importance to understand the vital role of cell-to-cell virus trafficking throughout the infected plant.

Cell adhesion measurements :

The AFM force spectroscopy has also been widely used to study the adhesive properties of living cells. Benoit *et al.*³⁸ (2000) measured the cell-cell adhesion of *Dictyostelium discoideum* cells, and found a minimal rupture force $f^* = 23 \pm 8$ pN.

Chen *et al.*³⁹ (2000) carried out a very interesting study on the increase of cell adhesion by receptor cross-linking. The receptor (concanavilin A) was coupled to the AFM tip via a biotin-avidin linkage, whereas the concanavilin A ligands were expressed on the surface of NIH3T3 fibroblast cells. Force measurements were performed before and after chemically cross-linking adhesion receptors on the surface of fibroblast cells with either DTSSP (3,3'-dithiobis[sulfosuccinimidyl]propionate) or glutaraldehyde. The observed increase in cell adhesion after cross-linking was attributed to an enhancement in the cooperativity among adhesion proteins resulting from the formation of multiple ligand-receptor bonds.

Zhang *et al.*⁴⁰ (2003) have further investigated the cooperative adhesion between ligand-receptor bonds by performing force spectroscopy experiments on (strept)avidin-biotin complexes. The observed changes in the pulling speed and binding affinity affected the cooperativity of (strept)avidin-biotin bonds. In particular, at slow pulling speed (210 nm/s) the ligand-receptor linkages broke sequentially (six peaks appeared on the force-distance curves, each peak corresponding to the rupture of one ligand-receptor bond). By contrast, at high separation rate (1950 nm/s) simultaneous rupture of (strept)avidin-biotin bonds was observed with only a maximum of two peaks appearing in the force-distance curves. Also, the influence of binding affinity on binding cooperativity was investigated. The binding affinity increased by using a higher pH buffer. Two sets of measurements were performed, at pH 6 and pH 10. The average rupture force increased with the pulling speed at both pH 6 and 10. However, the rupture force ($f^* = 0.57 \pm 0.07$ nN) measured at pH 10 was higher than that recorded ($f^* = 0.35 \pm 0.02$ nN) at pH 6. These results indicated that increase in pulling speed and binding affinity enhanced the cooperativity of ligand-receptor linkages.

Cell adhesion has been extensively measured at the single molecule level (see earlier discussion). However, Kim *et al.*¹⁶⁸⁻¹⁷⁰ measured the cell adhesive interaction at a cellular level. To achieve this, a microsphere (10 μ m diameter) was glued on to the end of an AFM cantilever in order to increase (~ 55 -fold) the contact area between the AFM probe and the cell surface. Three different ligand-receptor systems were studied. In the first experiment the microsphere was functionalised with fibronectin (ligand) and force spectroscopy measurements were carried out on living Balb 3T3 fibroblast cells¹⁶⁸. To determine the adhesion strength, a new parameter called separation work, having the dimension of energy (J), was introduced. The

separation work was defined as the integral of the area under the force-extension curve. The results showed that this parameter was a good measure of the specific interaction between the fibronectin and the cell surface. The second experiment¹⁶⁹ concerned the study of the time-course effects of lipopolysaccharide (LPS) + phorbol-12-myristate-13-acetate (PMA) on the adhesion interaction between type I collagen and C₆ glioma cells. The type I collagen was immobilised on the microsphere. The results showed that LSP/PMA affects the expression level of fibronectin; the adhesion strength of collagen being enhanced 1.7 and 1.6 times after 1 and 4 days from the seeding of cells, respectively. In the third experiment¹⁷⁰ the distribution of binding sites for vitronectin (a specific ligand of integrin $\alpha_v\beta_5$) on living murine osteoblastic cells was determined. Human vitronectin was covalently immobilised on the microsphere. The distribution of vitronectin receptors on the surface of the cell was investigated by measuring the cell adhesive strength between the functionalised microsphere and the cell expressing integrin $\alpha_v\beta_5$ (vitronectin receptor) on its surface. It was found that the binding sites for vitronectin were mostly covering the cell edges as also showed by immunohistochemistry experiments.

Kim and coworkers⁴¹ (2004) developed an AFM-based technique to determine with a very high sensitivity the number of receptors on cell surfaces. Knowing this parameter is important to investigate the mechanisms of molecular recognition between a ligand and its complementary receptor, as well as the responses of cells to stimulation. Force spectroscopy experiments were carried out to measure the separation work between the vitronectin-7 molecules (antigens) immobilised on a glass surface, and the anti-vitronectin-7 molecules (antibodies) immobilised on a microsphere. The sensitivity of the detection of antigens on the glass surface was determined by performing force measurements for different number densities ranging from 10 to 10⁶ antigens per micrometer square. As the number density of antigens was increased, the separation work became larger. The results indicated that this AFM-based technique should permit to distinguish 10-fold difference in sample concentrations, e.g., those of specific receptors on a cell surface.

Zhang *et al.*⁴² (2004) studied the molecular mechanism of leukocyte-endothelial interactions by carrying out real-time force spectroscopy experiments. A single living human promyelocytic leukemia cell (HL-60) was immobilised on to an AFM tip. Firstly, the interaction between the HL-60 cell and a monolayer of human um-

bilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) was measured over different positions in the monolayer, the detachment forces ranged from 40 to 100 pN. HL-60 adhesion was found to be larger at the edges formed by adjacent HUVECs. Secondly, the HUVEC monolayer was activated by TNF- α (tumour necrosis factor- α). The detachment force of HL-60 from the borders of the activated HUVEC monolayer was higher than that obtained when the HUVEC monolayer was not activated by TNF- α . The inhibitory effects of different function-blocking antibodies and a cyclic arginine-glycine-aspartic acid (cRGD) peptide were also studied. The HL-60 adhesion to the TNF- α activated HUVEC monolayer was significantly reduced by monoclonal antibodies (expressed on the surface of the HL-60 cell) against β_1 integrins (expressed on the surface of the HUVEC cells). However, HL-60-HUVEC adhesion was only partially inhibited by antibodies against selectins, ICAM-1, and VCAM-1, and it was not affected by anti- $\alpha_v\beta_3$. Also the cRGD peptide inhibited the HL-60-HUVEC adhesion. These results showed the importance of β_1 integrins and their ligands in HL-60-HUVEC adhesion.

2.3.2. Microrheology :

What is microrheology ?

Microrheology¹⁷¹ is another very important field of application of the AFM force spectroscopy. Generally speaking, the rheology concerns the study of the deformation and flow of a material when a force is applied. The solid samples store the energy up and give an elastic response similar to that given by a spring. By contrast, the liquid samples dissipate the energy through the viscous friction¹⁷².

It is necessary to distinguish between macrorheology and microrheology. The macrorheology allows precise characterisation of the viscoelastic properties of complex fluids, such as colloidal suspensions, gels, emulsions, or surfactant mixtures. Since the use of macrorheological technique requires millimetre-sized samples, these experimental methods are not suitable to study materials, of which only very small portions are available (e.g., biological samples). In addition, the macrorheological methods do not allow performing local measurements on inhomogeneous systems. These problems can be solved by using microrheological techniques¹⁷³ that permit to measure the viscoelastic properties of soft samples (e.g., biological systems) at a micrometer level. In particular, microrheological studies of biological samples elucidate phenomena involved in cell deformation, such as migration, extravasation, cell division, angiogenesis, embryo-

genesis, etc. In addition, it is possible to investigate the relation between the rheological properties of cells and their membrane properties. This permits to understand the strong correlation that exists between the viscoelastic and adhesive properties of cells.

Recently, many microrheological experiments have been performed on biological samples¹¹⁸ by using AFM in force spectroscopy mode. These experimental data were then analysed within the framework of theoretical contact mechanic models to derive the Young's modulus (elastic modulus), as well as the interaction forces between the biological system and a substrate (e.g., glass slides). Usually, the micropunch used to carry out microrheological experiments is the pyramidal tip of an AFM cantilever. However, Mahaffy and coworkers¹⁷⁴ (2000) employed a microsphere glued on to the end of an AFM cantilever to study the viscoelastic behaviour of thick regions of fibroblast cells with a controlled non-destructive stress range (100 Pa to 10 kPa). A microsphere instead of the AFM pyramidal tip was used to avoid damaging these soft samples.

This new punch geometry has also been employed by Dimitriadis *et al.*¹¹⁸ (2002) to measure the elastic modulus of PVA (Polyvinyl Alcohol) gels. Three main problems in using the AFM to measure the elastic modulus of soft materials were highlighted: (i) use of AFM pyramidal tip as a micropunch causes the Young's modulus value of the sample to be overestimated because the pyramidal tip induces some local constraints that cause it to go beyond the linear regime of the material; (ii) use of the Hertz model¹⁷⁵ to analyse the experimental data of thin (a few micron thick) samples introduces very large errors in the data. This is due to the fact that the Hertz model is based upon the hypothesis that the elasticity of the material is linear (i.e., the contact zone between the sample and the punch does not depend on the applied force) and that its thickness is infinite; (iii) it is very difficult to see the contact point and to define correctly the geometry of the contact region between a soft sample and the pyramidal tip because of the geometrical imperfections of the latter one.

A possible solution to the first and third problems is to use a microsphere as micropunch^{118,174}. Indeed, it causes smaller deformations than a normal pyramidal tip, and also the pressure applied on the sample is less (first problem). The geometry of the contact zone between the sample surface and the microsphere is better defined, and thus it is much easier to see the initial contact point (third problem). The second problem can be overcome by em-

ploying theoretical models that are not based upon the hypothesis of small deformations¹¹⁸. This is due to the fact that the real contact area between the AFM probe and the sample surface depends on the force applied by the probe on the sample. Consequently, large deformations might occur that have to be taken into account by the theoretical model used.

When microrheological AFM experiments on soft samples are performed in liquid, it is necessary to bear in mind that the hydrodynamic drag-force artefact, which is due to the viscous friction of the cantilever with the liquid, might affect the force measurements. Usually, the hydrodynamic drag-force value is estimated at a certain position above the sample and then subtracted from the contact force measured on the sample. However, this approach can underestimate the hydrodynamic drag-force value. Alcaraz *et al.*¹⁷⁶ (2002) assessed the effect of the hydrodynamic drag force at low Reynolds numbers[‡] ($Re < 1$). It was found that the drag force artefact can be accurately estimated by measuring the drag factor $b(h)$ at $h = 0$, i.e., when the tip and the sample are in contact, h being the distance between the AFM tip and the sample surface. These results, therefore, showed that to avoid any hydrodynamic drag-force artefact it is necessary to carry out contact microrheological experiments. Accurately correcting the drag-force might help to improve the scan speed in contact mode AFM imaging, as well as the pulling speed in AFM force spectroscopy measurements.

Measurements of viscoelastic and micromechanical properties of living cells:

During the past ten years, the AFM has found ever-increasing use to study viscoelastic properties of cells^{55,135,177}.

Dvorak *et al.*¹⁷⁸ (1998) developed an AFM-based method to study the kinetic changes in viscoelastic properties of living cells. In particular, the kinetic changes in the cell stiffness occurring during the mitotic cycle of living vertebrate cells were investigated, and a decrease in stiffness was found in the mitotic spindle region during anaphase.

A very interesting study of the architecture of cellular cytoskeleton (a 3-D network composed of actin filaments,

[‡]Fluid flow can be either laminar or turbulent. The factor that determines which type of flow is present is the ratio of inertial forces to viscous forces within the fluid, expressed by the nondimensional Reynolds number, Re .

intermediate filaments, and microtubules) was carried out by Wu *et al.*¹⁷⁹ (1998) who measured the elasticity, viscoelasticity, and plasticity (propensity of a material to undergo permanent deformation under load) of L929 cells. The cells were treated with cytochalasin D, nocodazole or colcemid, and it was observed that cytochalasin D reduced both the elasticity and cytoplasmic viscosity of cells. By contrast, nocodazole or colcemid induced a strong increase in the elasticity and a slight increase in the viscosity of L929 cells. The cell membrane and the cytoskeleton were found to be mechanically coupled. Cells that tightly adhered on to the substrate were much stiffer than those loosely attached. Also, it was found that the cells crosslinked with glutaraldehyde, DTSSP or concavilin A were stiffer than those untreated. In particular, only the cells crosslinked with concavilin A showed a plastic behaviour, indicating that concavilin A might induce a cytoskeletal reorganisation. A-Hassan *et al.*¹⁸⁰ (1998) developed an analytical approach, called force integration to equal limits (FIEL) mapping, to analyse the AFM force spectroscopy curves in order to create micromechanical maps providing information about the local cell elasticity. This experimental approach has the advantage to be independent of the tip-sample initial contact point and the cantilever spring constant. This method was used to investigate the viscoelastic properties of living Madine-Darby canine kidney (MDCK) cells, which are well-characterised epithelial cells. In order to get information about the cell elasticity only, the force-distance curves were collected on a time scale where the viscous contributions were negligible. The FIEL mapping showed that the cell elasticity was not coupled with the cell morphology.

Sato and coworkers⁴³ (2000) studied the morphology and mechanical properties of cultured bovine endothelial cells exposed to a shear stress of 2 Pa up to 24 h. A confocal microscope was used to obtain a 3-D image of a cell in order to precisely localise the cellular region where subsequent AFM force spectroscopy experiments were carried out. The stressed cells were found to be stiffer, and the stiffness increased with the exposure time. In particular, after 6 h exposure the stiffness was higher at the upstream side of the cells than the downstream side, whereas after 24 h exposure the stiffness was similar on both sides of the cell. These changes in the cell stiffness might be correlated to the distribution of stress fibres in the cell. Indeed, under stress conditions, such as a shear stress, the actin filaments (one of the components of the cytoskeleton, which is the main stress-bearing component of a cell) coalesce forming stress fibres that attach to

the adhesion sites of the cell-substrate interface.

Mathur *et al.*⁴⁴ (2000) used an AFM-TIRFM system to study simultaneously the transmission of force from the apical to the basal membrane (using AFM) and the dynamics of focal adhesion points (using TIRFM) of HUVEC cells. The cell basal membrane was fluorescently labelled and a constant force was applied on to the apical cell surface to study the effects of localised force application at the apical cell membrane on the cell's focal adhesion size and position at the basal cell membrane. It was found that applying a force of 0.3–0.5 nN for 1 min on the apical surface induced a change in the position and area of the focal adhesion points at the basal surface. In particular, the change in the focal adhesion area was much more evident when the force was applied over the nuclear region. By contrast, no significant changes in the focal adhesion area were recorded when the force was applied over the cell edge. These results suggested that the cell response to the localised applied force over the cell nucleus and edge was global, the nuclear region seeming to be stiffer (elastic modulus = 7.22 ± 0.46 kPa) than the rest of the cell body (elastic modulus = 2.97 ± 0.79 kPa near to the nucleus and 1.27 ± 0.36 kPa near the edge). In addition, it appeared that the nucleus and the focal adhesions were linked via the cytoskeleton.

Mathur and coworkers¹⁸¹ (2001) investigated the differences in the elastic modulus and viscous behaviour of cardiac and skeletal muscle cells and vascular endothelial cells. The accuracy of the measurements of these properties of the cells strongly depended upon the AFM probe velocity, indentation depth, and the assumed shape of the probe. In particular, the viscous behaviour was a function of the probe velocity, whereas the elastic modulus was dependent on the AFM probe geometry and the indentation depth with respect to the cell thickness. The AFM probe was modelled as either a cone or a blunt cone-spherical cap. Less variation in the elastic modulus with the indentation depth was obtained when the blunt cone-spherical cap geometry rather than conical geometry was considered. It was found that the cardiac cells were the stiffest (elastic modulus = 100.3 ± 10.7 kPa), the skeletal muscle cells were in the middle between the cardiac muscle and vascular endothelial cells (elastic modulus = 24.7 ± 3.5 kPa), and the endothelial cells were the softest with their elastic modulus ranging from 1.4 ± 0.1 kPa to 6.8 ± 0.4 kPa, depending on where the force was applied on to the cell surface. In addition, cardiac and skeletal muscle cells showed a nonlinear elastic behaviour. These results confirmed that the viscoelastic properties of the three types of cells vary according to

their functional and structural differences.

An important application of AFM force spectroscopy to study the cell's viscoelastic and mechanical properties is the AFM single-cell elastography⁴⁵. Generally, dynamic viscoelastic behaviours are investigated locally by indenting the cell body with the AFM probe. The AFM elastography combines imaging and indentation to generate a spatial distribution map of the mechanical properties of a cell, and this knowledge allows one to extract information about the structure and function of the cytoskeleton. This technique is sensible to the presence of disease in a single cell, and thus can be used as a disease marker. AFM elastography of living cells can be a powerful tool in medicine to enhance the detection, diagnosis, and treatment of diseases.

Mahaffy *et al.*⁴⁶ (2004) investigated the viscoelastic properties of both thin (<1000 nm) and thick (>1000 nm) areas of a fibroblast. Different theoretical models were applied in order to take into account the substrate effects. In particular, the Chen model¹⁸² was used to obtain the elastic constant and the Poisson ratio for very thin cell regions, such as the leading edge where the cytoskeleton adheres to the substrate. By contrast, for regions of the cell that are not strongly adhering to the substrate (e.g., areas far from the edge), the Tu model¹⁸³ was employed. Unlike the Chen model, the Tu model does not allow to obtain the Poisson ratio. For very thin cellular areas, an elastic constant of $\sim 1.6 \pm 0.2$ kPa and an experimentally determined Poisson ratio of ~ 0.4 to 0.5 , while for thick areas an elastic constant of $\sim 0.6 \pm 0.1$ kPa, were obtained. These results indicated that the leading edge zones (well adhered areas) of a cell are stiffer than the regions farther from the edge (non-adhered areas).

Sato and coworkers¹⁸⁴ (2004) studied the influence on cell elasticity of the changes in cell adhesion on cell matrices. The elasticity of HUVEC cells was measured and the experimental data were analysed in the framework of the Hertz model. In particular, the effects on cell elasticity of the cell culture period and the cell matrix, such as collagen (a component of the extracellular matrix quite often used as cell matrix in tissue engineering for regeneration), were investigated. The elasticity of the HUVEC cells depended on the culture period. It was also found that HUVEC cells cultured on type IV collagen-coated matrix showed much higher elasticity than those cultured on gelatine-coated matrix. These results suggest that the type IV collagen is a very good cell matrix for HUVEC cells.

Canetta *et al.*⁴⁷ (2005) measured the viscoelastic properties of single living cells by using an AFM-based force spectrometer. This homemade force spectrometer, set on an inverted microscope, provided two different visualisations¹⁸⁵, one from below (microscope) and one lateral (ultrazoom consisting of high magnification zoom lens and connected to a CCD camera). ICAM-1 transfected CHO (Chinese Hamster Ovary) cells were studied. In particular, two types of cells were analysed, CHO Ca 1-6 (cells expressing the complete ICAM-1 sequence, which can interact with the cytoskeleton) and CHO Δ -Cyto cells (ICAM-1 deleted from its cytoplasmic domain, which cannot bind to the cytoskeleton) (Fig. 12). The AFM probe used was a microsphere (~ 15 μ m diameter) functionalised with anti-ICAM-1 (Fig. 12) and attached to a tipless cantilever.

Fig. 12. Sketches of the Chinese Hamster Ovary cells, CHO Ca 1-6 (ICAM-1 is anchored to the cytoskeleton) and CHO Δ Cyto (ICAM-1 is not attached to the cytoskeleton) cells. Anti-ICAM-1 are shown on the bead side.

The cell-microsphere contact was therefore a plane-spherical one. After indenting the cell with the microsphere, the microsphere was vertically withdrawn at a pulling speed of 1 μ m/s and the cell deformation observed by using the lateral view (Fig. 13).

To determine the viscous and elastic properties of a single cell, the force-distance curves obtained from the force spectroscopy experiments were analysed within the framework of a model of filament stretching¹⁸⁶. It was found that the CHO Ca 1-6 cells have a two-fold higher elastic modulus (1.8 – 2.1 kPa) than the CHO Δ -Cyto cells

Fig. 13. Sequence of lateral images of the dynamic separation test on a CHO Ca 1-6 cell. The straight white line in (a) separates the real image of the cell-microsphere system from its reflection on the glass cover-plate. The microsphere first indents the cell and then it is withdrawn at a constant pulling speed of $1 \mu\text{m/s}$. The formation of a long tiny filament is shown. (a)-(f) Observation time $t = 0, 6, 11, 14, 22, 38$ s, respectively. At $t = 38$ s, the detachment of the cell from the functionalized microsphere occurs.

(0.9–1.2 kPa), indicating that the presence of interactions between ICAM-1 and the cytoskeleton increased the cell elasticity.

3. Summary and future work

It is clear from the discussion on the previous pages that AFM has become a very powerful tool in a relatively short time to study biological samples in their native environments. During this period, AFM imaging has been extensively used to study the structures and functions of biomolecules, e.g., DNA, proteins; and visualise the conformational changes of microbial cell surfaces, e.g., bacteria, membranes, yeast cells. The very high resolution of AFM has allowed real-time investigation of the dynamics of DNA-protein interactions.

AFM's capability to measure interaction forces at a single molecule level has opened new horizons in mo-

lecular biology. The unbinding forces of ligand-receptor bonds, e.g., antigen-antibody; and individual molecules, e.g., DNA, have been widely investigated. In biophysics, AFM represents a precious and unique instrument to study cell adhesion, mechanical, and microrheological properties of biological specimens.

A recent application of AFM is the nanomanipulation of biological systems (nanobiomanipulation). The possibility to combine AFM with other microscopic techniques, such as AFM-IM, AFM-FM, AFM-TIRFM has added further dimensions to this already fast-growing field. In particular, AFM-FM and AFM-TIRFM systems increase its versatility for future applications to nanobiotechnology by precise manipulation of single molecules. Also, nanosurgery of living cells is a new field that will catch up very fast. The development of advanced techniques to modify the shapes of AFM tips to obtain ultrathin needles that can be used to penetrate at precise positions inside the cells, will allow us to modify the cell's functions. This will have a huge impact in nanomedicine, and in particular in the stem cell research to control cells' differentiation and proliferation.

Nowadays, AFM technology is growing even at a faster pace. New AFMs to image a broader range of biological samples at much higher resolutions, and new methodologies to detect the relative motion of the AFM cantilever, to construct smaller and lighter cantilevers for improving the detection of very weak force interactions, to improve the control of the sample environment during scanning and force measurements, are being developed. A new chamber, in which the temperature can be varied and CO_2 gas flushed, has been developed (JPK Instruments) recently, and this can be used to study single molecules or living cells in an environment where, for example, they can stay alive and continue to grow.

A combination of AFM with optical tweezers (AFM-OT) should permit in future to increase the range of detectable forces to $\sim 0 \text{ pN}$ – $0.1 \mu\text{N}$. It would also be possible to trap a single molecule or a living cell with OT and visualise with AFM, in real-time, the changes in the sample morphology while it undergoes mechanical stresses, such as stretching or compression. The main drawback of AFM-FM is that the wavelength of the AFM laser kills the weak fluorescent signal, making it difficult to detect precisely the fluorescent sample. With the recent development in the technique where a normal red laser has been replaced with an infrared (IR) laser (JPK Instrument), it will become possible in the future to study weak fluorescent samples.

The recent marketing of a product VideoAFM™ (Infinitesima Ltd. trademark) will allow real-time imaging at video frame rates. This will permit to follow dynamic processes with millisecond resolution while imaging at the same time.

These are just some examples of new developments in the AFM technology. Other developments concern the software used to analyse the AFM data in order to extract as much information as possible from both the images and force-distance curves. It is beyond doubt that the AFM is becoming indispensable and expanding further to bridge the cultural barriers between different disciplines that cover life sciences, biophysics, nanobiotechnology, chemistry, physics, material sciences, engineering, and medicine.

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